

Enantiodromia and Integrality: The Rhythm of the Cultural Continuum

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1. Introduction

The human cultural continuum is in a critical phase of transformation. Over the next several generations, the evolution of consciousness along that continuum may well determine the future of humanity and, perhaps, the degree to which we will remain fully human. Rapid developments in computer technology, cybernetics and artificial intelligence now have some futurists predicting a cybernetic-human synthesis that could ultimately transform humanity into something *other*. Science fiction gives us a picture of this future as often alluring and inevitably frightening.

Emphasizing this infatuation with technology and the interface between human and artificial intelligence, the K-12 educational curriculum is focused on science, technology, engineering and math (STEM). This curriculum captivates the individual and collective imagination and subtly implies that the interface with technology is more important than our relationships with humanity, our community, our families, and our world. The more prominent this attitude becomes, the more important it is to find a balance that makes technology subservient to the preservation of our humanity.

For some 2,500 generations our humanity has been preserved because adults taught each successive generation to be carriers of the culture. While this fundamental concept should guide the development of a K-12 cultural curriculum, it is not enough just to *study* the cultural continuum; we must each traverse this pathway into the future. Re-visioning the K-12 curriculum to emphasize the humanities and embrace the evolution in consciousness teaches young people to be the carriers of the cultural continuum into the future. To better understand what this means to education, we can look at two concepts that shape the rhythm of the cultural continuum: *enantiodromia* and *integrality*.

2. Enantiodromia

Applied to the cultural continuum, *enantiodromia* describes a wave-like pattern — an ever-changing dynamic flow between poles — rather than an overcoming of cultural obstacles in a direct, linear progression.

The concept of enantiodromia originated with the pre-Socratic Greek philosopher Heraclitus around 500 BC. “[All] Pre-Socratic thinkers were struck by the dominance of change in the world of our experience. Heraclitus ... probably expressed the universality

of change more clearly and more dramatically than his predecessors; but for him it was the complementary idea of the *measure* inhering in change, the stability that persists through it and controls it, that was of vital importance” (Kirk, Raven, and Schofield 186). In Carl Jung’s more psychological definition, enantiodromia is likened to a “play of opposites,” a dynamic flow in the course of events where “everything that exists turns into its opposite.” For example, day turns to night and night to day; life to death and death back into life. Jung says, “Just as all energy proceeds from opposition, so the psyche too possesses its inner polarity ... as Heraclitus realized long ago” (Jung and Jaffe 346). This polarity in the psyche, says Jung, is an indispensable prerequisite to life.

Thus, psychologically, enantiodromia describes a dynamic intercourse between the inner poles that Jung defines as distinct psychological fields: the fields of the unconscious and of consciousness. These are complementary polarities in the psyche that communicate through the *transcendent function*: the stability that Heraclitus sought that persists through transformation. This important, defining element in the rhythm of the cultural continuum can be applied to pedagogical technique as well as to the curriculum.

The first application of Jungian psychology to education pertains to education’s first objective: to develop consciousness in the child. The field of thinking consciousness is not an *a priori* condition of the psyche but grows with the processes of psychological development and education. However, “The psyche of the child in its preconscious state is anything but a *tabula rasa*; it is already preformed in a recognizable individual way, and is moreover equipped with all specifically human instincts, as well as with the *a priori* foundations of the higher functions” (Jung and Jaffe 348). Thus, nurturing and developing the field of consciousness is an open-ended, two-sided process.

On the one hand, we gather information from the natural, cultural, and social environments of the external world. This process requires attention to factual details. As consciousness matures over time, the process will configure facts into cogent hypotheses about the nature of external reality. In formal education, the objective is not just to learn how to gather factual information and form hypotheses, but also to inculcate a critical reasoning capacity to apply to those hypotheses.

However, if this development of the field of consciousness remains one-sided — that is, if it is focused on the thinking function and the world of external reality — then it neglects the transcendent function that maintains the connection to inner reality. Critical reason, when *not* guided by the transcendent function, subtly incorporates into itself the cultural biases of collective consciousness, as for example distortions of history or the rigidity of cultural mores. These biases are used to construct a “mass psyche.” This biased, one-sided model — STEM — now dominates K-12 education in the United States, and perhaps in much of the rest of the industrial world (Mitchell).

In contrast, the open-ended, two-sided development of consciousness is evident in more holistic models of education. The drive behind holistic education is given meaning in a simple and succinct statement by Jung:

Reason sets the boundaries [of life] far too narrowly for us.... The more the critical reason dominates, the more impoverished life becomes; but the more of the unconscious, and the more of myth we are capable of making conscious, the more of life we integrate. Overvalued reason has this in common with political absolutism: under its dominion, the individual is pauperized. (Jung and Jaffe 302)

Thus, our culturally biased views of reality are tempered by making conscious the contents of the unconscious. Becoming conscious of psychic material that exists in the unconscious comes from the observation and interpretation of the non-rational *intuitive, instinctive, imaginative* and *feeling-toned* perceptions that emerge in symbolic form as *dreams, premonitions, and synchronistic events*.

Just as consciousness of *external* reality is developed in education by the rational acquisition and critical assessment of facts, consciousness of *internal* reality is developed in education by emphasizing the tools of interpretation. Primary among those tools — tools that can be taught at elementary and secondary education levels — is the symbolism inherent in fairy tales, mythology and the arts. These symbols manifest in expressions that give form to the spiritual forces of the archetypes in the culture and exist in the collective imagination rather than in collective consciousness.

A holistic model of education teaches interpretation, understanding, acceptance and assimilation of influences from the unconscious — that is, the influences of the instincts and archetypes. Jung says,

The archetypes, which are pre-existent to consciousness and condition it, appear in the part they actually play in reality: as a priori structural forms of the stuff of consciousness. They do not in any sense represent things as they are in themselves, but rather the forms in which things can be perceived and conceived.... They account only for the collective component of a perception. (Jung and Jaffe 347)

Thus, the acquisition of a repertoire of archetypal symbols is essential to developing consciousness. The goal of becoming conscious of one's own true nature cannot be served by a one-sided development. Enantiodromia, which allows communication between the conscious and unconscious poles of the psyche, is a significant factor in shaping both pedagogical technique and the curriculum so that both can serve the educational objective of developing consciousness in the child.

The second principle of Jungian psychology that can be applied to the K-12 classroom involves the relationship between the child's developing consciousness and the human cultural continuum. Jung says, "Consciousness is phylogenetically and ontogenetically a secondary phenomenon" (Jung and Jaffe 348). Therefore, "Attainment of consciousness is culture in the broadest sense, and self-knowledge is therefore the heart and essence of this process" (Jung and Jaffe 324-325). This concept justifies a redesigned cultural education curriculum (Mitchell).

For Jung, the principle *Ontogeny Recapitulates Phylogeny* implies that individual development carries forward the earlier psychical structures of human development. “If the unconscious is anything at all, it must consist of earlier evolutionary stages of our conscious psyche” (Jung and Jaffe 348). Jung describes these “evolutionary stages” in a psychological context that supports ontogenetic development, rather than in terms of phylogenetic evolution. The instincts and archetypes that Jung describes psychologically as inherited qualities (Jung, *Structure* 133) are the contents of the collective unconscious that are brought to consciousness in symbolic form. The integration of unconscious content into mental ego-consciousness is what Jung describes as the transformative process of individuation. This psychological explanation is ontologically beneficial, but it does not provide a complete picture because it does not address the phylogenetic evolution of consciousness on which the ontological model is based.

To examine these “earlier evolutionary stages of our conscious psyche” (Jung and Jaffe 348) from the perspective of the cultural continuum and the evolution of consciousness, we can turn to one of Jung’s contemporaries, the German-Swiss cultural philosopher Jean Gebser. Born in Prussia in 1905, Gebser lived in Spain and Paris in the 1930s and entered Switzerland just before the border was closed in 1939. He lived the rest of his life in Bern. His opus, *The Ever-Present Origin*, was published in 1954. Gebser lectured in Zürich in the 1950s and ‘60s, and there is anecdotal evidence that Gebser and Jung knew each other, but no record of professional correspondence between them has yet surfaced. Nonetheless Gebser’s description of structures in the evolution of consciousness provides a cultural background for Jung’s transformative process of individuation.

Gebser describes four successive structures in the phylogenetic development of consciousness — the archaic, the magical, the mythic, and the mental — that have traced an enantiomorphic pattern along the cultural continuum and form the pattern of our ontological development as well. The fifth structure of consciousness, the one we are currently engaged in discovering — integrality — defines a synergistic integration of the preceding four structures.

3. Integrality: The Structures of Consciousness and the Rhythm of the Cultural Continuum

Integrality is more than a simple integration of earlier consciousness structures. “[The] process, which makes the integral consciousness structure accessible, is a new capacity, and not a mere sum of the old” (Gebser 543). That is, its wholeness lies beyond the instinctive unity of archaic consciousness, beyond the emotional power of magical consciousness, beyond the imagery and complementarity of mythic consciousness, and beyond the division and synthesis of mental consciousness. Gebser’s concept of integrality describes culturally what Jung describes psychologically, drawing archaic, magical, and mythic consciousness out of the unconscious and into a new unity with mental consciousness. Individuation and integrality, together, describe the next level in the evolution of consciousness in the individual *and* in humanity, and offer another

possible outcome to humanity's progression through the cultural continuum: to become most completely human.

Gebser's four structures of consciousness that precede integrality are represented enantiodynamically by both *efficient* and *deficient* modes. These opposing modes of the four sequential consciousness structures provide us with the phylogenetic pattern for ontological development, as follows.

3.1. Archaic Consciousness

This structure of consciousness belongs to our distant past and is "[t]he structure closest to and presumably originally identical with the origin." Gebser continues, "It is akin, if not identical, to the original state of biblical paradise: a time where the soul is yet dormant, a time of complete non-differentiation of man and the universe" (Gebser 43).

From an evolutionary perspective, it belongs to a period of human development that lacks a defined sense of self. Though connected to the world, one had no sense of being "in the world" because there was no central point of reference — no sense of self — from which to relate to space and time. Relationship to the world occurred through instinct, presentiment, and impulse. Living in small social groups, "humanity" existed in a passive relationship to the natural environment.

Though we may hold a vision of bipedal humanoids existing in the archaic past of our evolutionary biology, we are compelled to imagine the archaic structure of consciousness more symbolically. In its *efficient* mode, humanity existed in a balanced union between nature and divine consciousness — an idyllic existence; a Garden of Eden. The *deficient* mode of archaic consciousness is represented by the "fall": expulsion from the garden; alienation from both nature and divine consciousness.

Ontologically, this archaic structure of consciousness is evident in the newborn child during the first year of life. In his book *The Child*, Erich Neumann calls it the extra-uterine embryonic phase in which the child remains in a "unitary reality" with the mother. He says, "In the pre-ego stage characteristic of earliest childhood ... the child is still contained within its mother, though its body is already born" (Neumann, *Child* 11).

It is difficult to find a clear picture of this unitary reality in modern society. However, in her book *The Continuum Concept*, Jean Liedloff describes it very succinctly in terms of the nurturance instinct. Liedloff documented this complex physical-emotional bond between mother and child from her experience living with the Yequana, a South American Indian tribe, in the 1950s. She compares the nurturance instinct — leading to healthy, happy children — to the loss of that instinct in the childrearing techniques of modern culture, often leading to an over-stressed, unhappy childhood.

Liedloff describes the continuum concept as an instinctive "good sense" that guided human behavior for eons, but that in the past few thousand years has been brought into disrepute. "[O]ur innate sense of what is best for us is short-circuited by suspicion while

the intellect, which has never known much about our real needs, decides what to do.” She continues, “It is not, for example, the province of the reasoning faculty to decide how a baby ought to be treated. We have had exquisitely precise instincts, expert in every detail of child care, since long before we became anything resembling *Homo sapiens*” (Liedloff 21-22).

As noted above, Jung understood the instincts and archetypes that make up the collective unconscious as *a priori* conditions of the child’s pre-conscious psyche. He postulates five “basic instincts”: hunger, sexuality, activity, reflection, and creativity (Jung, *Structure* 118). The instincts generate physically perceived impulses, pressures, and desires. Jung uses a simile from physics, suggesting that when instincts are charged with enough energy (perhaps through the parents’ nurturance instinct) they jump valence and become archetypal (Jung, *Structure* 212). The archetypes are spiritual, and produce images, ideas, and intuition, the source of which the child is aware of only a-perceptively. That is, instinctual and archetypal forces exist in counterpoise to rational-mental consciousness that will become centered in the developing ego. Liedloff’s continuum concept acknowledges this charge differential and advocates developing a free flow of information between the continuum of innate awareness and developing consciousness. The axis of this free flow of information, in Jungian terms, is the transcendent function.

Liedloff presents a vivid example of how the *efficient* mode of the archaic structure of consciousness is fostered in the child through nurturing the child’s natural exploration and auto-discovery of its instincts. But modern society tends toward propagating the *deficient* mode — a fracturing of the individual’s unity with nature and divine consciousness through the disruption of the continuum concept.

It begins with traumatic separation of the baby and the mother at birth and the placement of the child in the nursery ward, physically isolated from the mother. At home, infants are separated from the mother in nurseries, cribs, strollers and baby carriages, rather than sleeping with and being carried by her. “The violent tearing apart of the mother-child continuum ... may understandably result in depression for the mother, as well as agony for the infant” (Liedloff 36). This is equivalent to being alienated from the natural environment that, for the infant, is the mother’s body, and also alienated from proximity to “the ever-present origin.” This proximity is carried in what Neumann refers to as the “two-footedness” of the archetypal bond between mother and child:

When two human beings are united by a powerful bond, their mutual appetency forms a bilateral connection between them, releasing corresponding archetypes in the psyches of each other. So it takes two individuals to effect or set in motion these transpersonal factors of archetypes.... Once we have grasped this interhuman reality and the ‘two footedness’ of the archetype, it will be clear to us that an archetype cannot be evoked by any spontaneous process within the psyche.... (Neumann, *Child* 85-86)

The concept of the two-footedness of the archetype implies that the Mother archetype, expressed as the mother's nurturance instinct, stimulates the child's auto-evocation of instinctual drives out of the Child archetype that resides in the Self: the child's own "godhead"; the "ever-present origin."

The deficient side to the archaic structure of consciousness in modern societies ignores the psychological significance of mother-child bonding. This alienates the child from the nurturance instinct and can result in the "wounded child syndrome." Without grounding in the two-footedness of the archetype, the child's survival depends not on nurtured instincts but on the premature and distorted development of a self-identity built on foundations of frustration, stress, and rage. This can manifest in personality disorders, some symptoms of which are lack of an ability to give and receive affection, self-destructive behaviors, cruelty to self and others, phoniness, extreme control problems, lack of friendships, and learning disorders (Magid and McKelvey 254-257). There are many such children in modern societies that, to varying degrees, come to exhibit socio-pathological personality disorders that are evident to every classroom teacher. This deficient mode of archaic consciousness lies at the root of some of our most significant individual, psychological, social, and cultural problems.

3.2. *Magical Consciousness*

The magical structure of consciousness began to evolve in the timeless pre-historic past. Gebser attributes five characteristics to the magical structure of consciousness: 1) egolessness — there is no individual ego-self, but there is an emerging collective ego of the tribe or clan; 2) visible interchangeability of the real with the symbolic; 3) spacelessness and timelessness; 4) an active merging with nature in order to control it; and 5) a magic reaction to this merging, which gives mankind power (Gebser 48).

With this growing consciousness — which is not centered in the individual, but rather in the collective — there is a sense of freedom from the power of nature. Gebser says,

Man replies to the forces streaming toward him with his own corresponding forces: he stands up to Nature ... then he begins to be conscious of his own *will*. Witchcraft and sorcery ... are the natural means by which he seeks to free himself from the transcendent power of nature (Gebser 46)

Ontologically, the magical structure of consciousness appears in the domain of young children. In its *efficient* form, also depicted in Liedloff's continuum concept, we find the child securely embedded in the group ego of the family, clan, or tribe. Another manifestation of magical consciousness is that of the imaginary friend, where the numinous, or spiritual, takes form in the child's imagination and a visible interchangeability occurs between the real and the symbolic. It also is a fundamental characteristic of fairy tales. And it is evident in the way a small child senses his or her ability to merge with and have power over nature. Walt Whitman captured the efficient mode of magical consciousness most succinctly in a poem that begins:

There was a child went forth every day,
And the first object he looked upon, that object he became,
And that object became a part of him for the day or a certain part of the day,
Or for many years or stretching cycles of years. (Whitman 108)

Of this efficient mode of magical consciousness, Gebser says, “Only where the magic structure in the individual still works through impulse and instinct [that is, without knowing; without consciousness] does it realize its eminent, life-dispensing value in our day and age” (Gebser 60). It is an emotional, somatic quality, evident in the mystical participation of the archetypal mother-child bond; in the empathetic identification evident in twins and in lovers; in the communication between humans and animals; in telepathy; and in Jung’s concept of synchronicity (Neville, “Towards Integrality”).

However, as with the archaic structure of consciousness, the dominant mode of magical consciousness today is *deficient*. The power structure in modern society is obsessed, not with actively merging with nature, but with controlling nature from the outside — attempting to decipher the “laws of nature” and apply technology to control it. That control over nature extends to controlling human nature, as well. Gebser says,

All magic ... occurs in the natural-vital, egoless, spaceless and timeless sphere. This requires — as far as present-day man is concerned — a sacrifice of consciousness; it occurs in the state of trance, or when the consciousness dissolves as a result of mass reactions, slogans, or “isms.” (49)

There is great danger in this deficient mode of magical consciousness. Erich Neumann says, “The building up of the persona, and the adaptation to reality under the guidance of the superego [the collectivity] as the court of consciousness, [constellates] the mass man” (*Origins* 438-439). Additionally, Jung warns, “The collective attitude hinders the recognition and evaluation of a psychology different from the subject’s, because the mind that is collectively oriented is quite incapable of thinking and feeling in any other way than by projection” (*Psychological Types* 10).

The mass psyche, the deficient mode of magical consciousness, obstructs communication between the conscious and unconscious poles of the psyche and subverts the transcendent function. To the degree that the mass psyche directs the educational model of standardization, it becomes increasingly difficult for individuals to assess the instincts and archetypes and regain the momentum toward individuation and integrality.

3.3. Mythic Consciousness

The mythic structure of consciousness began to emerge with the Great Mother cults of the Neolithic Era, but it evolved in stages that overlapped the magical structure up to the rise of the great classic civilizations. Here we find the seeds of identity defined as soul. As the sense of soul developed, there was a growing temporal and spatial awareness.

Time was experienced rhythmically, through the cycles of the seasons. Space was experienced numinously, so that the emerging soul was connected spiritually to all things through the symbolic imagination. That connection was exemplified in mythology, conveyed through poetry and the visual arts, and taught to successive generations through an initiation/education process.

Gebser says, “the essential characteristic of the mythical structure is the emergent awareness of soul” (61). “The mythical structure ... has an imaginatory consciousness reflected in the imagistic nature of myth and responsive to the soul” (Gebser 67).

Today, we see an active mythological structure of consciousness in anthropological studies and in psychology. Dreams, visions, fantasies, and delusional ideas open up “a field of psychic phenomena which are themselves the matrix of all mythology” (Jung, *Symbols* 390).

In its *efficient* mode, mythological consciousness conveys the sense that humans have a role to play in the dynamic unfolding of a cosmic drama designed by the gods and told through mythologies. Thus, the cultural period when the efficient mode of mythological consciousness was most dominant was the Heroic Age. Heroes existed as personalities that took upon themselves the numinous, archetypal mythologem in order to bring some benefit to the community:

The hero himself appears as a being of more than human stature. He is distinguished from the very beginning by his godlike characteristics. Since he is psychologically an archetype of the self, his divinity only confirms that the self is numinous, a sort of god, or having some share in the divine nature..... The hero is the protagonist in God’s transformation of man. (Jung, *Symbols* 391-392)

Today, because of the modern ego’s involvement, we would call this psychological inflation. But the Heroic Age was pre-egoic in the sense that individual self-awareness emanated from the archetypal spiritual imagination rather than from the mental structure of consciousness. The heroes lived their myths by embodying personality patterns established by the gods. These myths evolved into re-enactments in ritual and in the arts.

Thus, the imaginative characteristic of the mythological structure of consciousness, and its manifestation in the arts and literature, provides the repertoire of symbols that lead directly to the acceptance, interpretation, understanding, and assimilation of the dreams, premonitions, and synchronistic events that emerge out of the unconscious and are drawn toward integration into consciousness.

Developmentally, the mythological structure lies in the natural domain of children. When the imagination is firmly grounded in the mythic structure of consciousness, it anchors the soul-end of a complementary polarity between the soul and the emerging ego. Jung, Neumann, Edinger, and others have called this polarity-link the ego-self axis. This axis — the transcendent function — maintains communication between the mythological,

imaginal soul-consciousness of the child and the emerging mental ego-consciousness of the adult.

The *deficient* mode of mythological consciousness is characterized by breaking communication through the depletion of the imaginative — symbolic — function of the psyche and a depletion of the individual's ability to interpret and assimilate the symbolic language of the unconscious. Here, it would be overstating the obvious to enumerate all the ways in which the modern educational system and modern culture diminish the imagination of the child and produce the *deficient* mode of mythological consciousness. We no longer carry mythological narratives within us, though they are carried for us in books and in often-distorted forms of mass media and virtual reality. But the greater poverty lies in our growing inability to accept and understand the mythological symbolism as a defining part of our humanity, rather than a fantasy projection.

This assault on the imaginative faculty disrupts the enantiodromic intercourse between the ego and the archetypal self, causing the personality to become centered in the ego and its relationship to the collectivity. The seat of consciousness shifts to the cultural superego, and the ego becomes a servant of what Jung calls “the spirit of the age” (Jung, *Structure* 340). This is a definitive act of socialization that disrupts the continuity of the child's holistic development. And this, in turn, results in the disrupted continuity of the cultural continuum as it is recapitulated in the development of the individual personality.

Some children are instinctively aware of being separated from an identity that has its origin as an a-perceptive archetypal image in the soul, but often they are incapable of articulating a response, though many suffer greatly for it. This may be one reason why so many young people turn away from education, with its single-minded emphasis on developing a dominating, standardized, culturally biased rational-mental structure of consciousness and identity. Yet without an education that teaches an alternative, young people still fall victim to the collectivity's hold on the individual's consciousness and personality through the mass psyche.

3. 4. *Mental Consciousness*

Gebser equates the rise of the mental structure of consciousness with the rise of the “law giver.” Among the Israelites, this figure arises with Moses, around 1225 BC, about the same time that the patriarchal Greeks defeated the matriarchal Trojans to end the mythological Golden Age. But Gebser also sites as examples the Indian lawgiver Manu, the Cretan King Minos, and Menes, the pharaoh who united Upper and Lower Egypt:

Wherever the law giver appears, he upsets the old equilibrium (mythical polarity), and in order to re-establish it, laws must be fixed and established. Only a mental world requires laws; the mythical world, secure in the polarity, neither knows nor needs them. (Gebser 76)

The centering of the personality in the ego is the primary characteristic of the mental structure of consciousness. A cultural superego emerges out of a collective mentality

reminiscent of the magical, tribal structure of consciousness and vies with the mythological archetypes for dominance over the developing personality. This development does not unfold to reveal the soul, as in mythological consciousness, but unfolds to reveal the ego and its progressive capacity to express complex, abstract cognitive structures. The ego becomes the new subjective center from which to make temporal and spatial assessments about the natural, social, and cultural environments and the nature of reality. Time becomes linear, sequential and quantifiable. Space is perceived in three dimensions. Reality is increasingly divided through subject-object duality. Spirit is perceived increasingly in abstract, prosaic terms rather than in poetic images.

In its *efficient* mode the mental structure of conscious is integrated with the efficient modes of both the mythic and magical structures. For example, in classical Athens or renaissance Florence, conceptual thinking was combined with a rich imaginative and symbolic life (Neville, "Towards Integrality"). Gebser points to the pre-Socratic Age, when all citizens were predisposed toward initiation into the mystery cults — which kept the collective spiritual imagination alive in them. Poetic language and proximity to myth distinguished early, pre-Socratic philosophy from later philosophical systems.

Coming to a similar conclusion about pre-Socratic Greece, Jung says, "The weird and wonderful nature of the gods was a self-evident fact in a hundred living myths and assumed a special significance in the no less credible philosophical refinements of those myths" (Jung, *Aion* 177). It is important to note that the 300 years of the pre-Socratic philosophers — when the mytho-magical and emerging mental structures of consciousness were in some degree of balance — was also a time when democratic consciousness flourished in the Greek polis.

Gebser goes on to say that the proliferation of philosophical systems — after about 300 B. C. — is accompanied by a proportional decrease of mythical elements (84). He says that mental consciousness began its decline toward the *deficient* aspect with Lao-Tse in China, the Buddha in India, and Socrates in Greece.

About Socrates, Nietzsche wrote, "Whereas in all truly productive men instinct is the strong, affirmative form and reason the dissuader and critic, in the case of Socrates the roles are reversed: instinct is the critic, consciousness the creator" (Nietzsche 84-85). This reversal characterizes the deficient mode of mental consciousness by emphasizing the power of mental abstraction. What Nietzsche emphasizes is the importance of the a-rational instincts as the driving creative force and the suggestion that mental consciousness should be the refining, critical element in the creative process.

Jung builds on this concept. Using a simile from modern physics, he says that when the instincts acquire a certain amount of energy, they jump valence to become archetypal. This is the foundation of creativity. The sequence from archaic creative instinct to the magical, emotional power to direct nature, to mythological imagination, to critical mental consciousness, can be read as a creative-consciousness continuum in its most efficient form.

The final stage in the deficient mode of mental consciousness — the rational-mental phase — began to blossom with the European Age of Enlightenment, which denigrated mysticism and systematized the abstract way of looking at reality. When the rational-mental phase dominates the psyche, the deficient modes of the archaic, magical, and mythic structures of consciousness all converge in the shadows of the unconscious. These deficient modes affect our perception of reality. Through education we emphasize the dominance of the rational-mental phase of consciousness, trapping the archaic, magical, and mythic modes in the unconscious.

Ontologically, the mental structure of consciousness begins to dominate the personality during the years of early adolescence. It results in an egoic-rationalistic way of looking at reality through the lens of what child psychologist Jean Piaget called formal operations, or abstract-conceptualization. One result of this is that many young people are fearful of expressing their singular uniqueness — the “true” nature of their soul. They are timid in expressing their instinctive creativity, and they are neurotically self-conscious about conforming to the collective behavioral norms of the peer group. Some of these characteristics are “normal” aspects of creating a strong ego-consciousness that will eventually strive toward integration and individuation. However, where the deficient mode of mental consciousness is most dominant they become symptomatic of a mass mentality that poses grave dangers because it breaks the link between the individual and the culture continuum. How did we go from the liberating promise of higher consciousness to being trapped in the mass psyche?

The post-Darwinian concept of the evolution of consciousness evolved into the widely accepted conclusion that *Ontogeny Recapitulates Phylogeny*. In a linear progression, rational-mental consciousness is necessarily considered superior to what the 19th century anthropologist Lucien Lévy-Bruhl called the *participation mystique* of “primitives.” It was believed that the child, like the “primitive,” existed in a state of mystical participation with reality (see Mousalimas 33, note 1). From the standpoint of consciousness development, the child’s psyche was a *tabula rasa* upon which consciousness, in its highly developed mental-rational form, could be written. Additionally, the theory of cultural evolution espouses the idea that Western culture — with over 400 years of Enlightenment — is superior to cultures still grounded in a more balanced perspective. Thus, the linear-historical view of the development of consciousness and the hierarchical view of Western cultural superiority remain deeply ingrained in our educational philosophy and curriculum.

The advent of depth psychology at the beginning of the 20th century is responsible for arguing that the mental structure of consciousness cannot be divorced from its foundational roots in archaic, magical and mythic consciousness and does not offer a sufficient finale to the question of the evolution of consciousness. It is only logical to assume that it is, therefore, not an adequate terminal to the problem of educating children. This brings us to the concept of integrality as the next step in consciousness’s evolution.

3. 5. *Integrality*

Integrality, which describes the next stage in the evolution of consciousness, has surfaced in both Eastern and Western philosophies. In the views of these philosophies, each of us carries within us the seed of Divine Consciousness. It could be called the *spark of divinity* at the core of the psyche, or could be equated to Jung's concept of the Self. Gebser called it the "ever-present origin."

The developmental objective is to transcend the state in which the ego dominates the personality — that is, to transcend the egoic-rationalistic mode of mental consciousness on which modern culture, with all of its technological advances, is based. Jung says that we have within us an inherent tendency called the transcendent function:

The tendencies of the conscious and the unconscious are the two factors that together make up the transcendent function. It is called "transcendent" because it makes the transition from one attitude to another organically possible, without loss of the unconscious. (Jung, *Structure* 73)

This fundamental idea of the individuation process gives us the capacity to transcend the ego's dominant position without dissolution, maintaining the integrity of the personality while expanding consciousness.

But transcendence on both the individual level and the level that transforms humanity takes place over generations and requires two adjustments to the way we educate our children: 1) it requires an education that teaches the acceptance, awareness and assimilation of archetypal images — that is, the significance of living a "symbolic life" relevant to one's chosen vocation; and 2) it requires a curriculum that teaches the enantiodromic flow of the cultural continuum rather than a linear view of history. This enables the twin processes of individuation-integrality to progress toward the next stage in the evolution of consciousness.

Gebser is also clear on the need to re-visualize educational philosophy from a mentally oriented, utilitarian model to one that reintegrates the structures of consciousness that have been repressed into the unconscious:

If our consciousness ... cannot master the new reality and make possible its realization, then the prophets of doom will have been correct. Other alternatives are an illusion; consequently, great demands are placed on us, and each one of us have been given a grave responsibility, not merely to survey but to actually traverse the path opening before us. (Gebser 5)

Jung has stated the problem very succinctly. He contends that the spirit of the age will not let itself be trifled with: "It is the popular way of thinking, and therefore it is decent, reasonable, scientific, and normal" (*Structure* 340). Thus, the "spirit of the age" is the greatest impediment to the evolution of consciousness. What needs to change is the kind

of thinking that is perpetuated in our schools, and the realization that the new structure of consciousness correlates Gebser's concept of Integrality with Jung's concept of individuation.

4. Integrality and Individuation

Because individuation is a transformative adventure that takes place over a lifetime, the seeds of individuation must be nurtured from an early age in the home and in the school. Thus, to preserve the drive toward individuation and integrality requires a cultural educational curriculum that teaches the rhythm of the cultural continuum. *Enantiodromia* gives definition to the dynamic intercourse between the conscious and unconscious poles of the psyche, as opposed to a linear progression from *participation mystique* to mental consciousness. *Integrality* gives us a cultural objective to teach our children. And *individuation* is the psychological process that draws the conscious and unconscious fields together into a holistic personality. Together, these three processes inform the next level in individual and cultural evolution, based on an integrative model.

Why consider such drastic changes to education? Psychologically, the conflict between one's true nature and the demands of the collectivity begins to emerge most prominently in early adolescence. But the child's natural tendency toward separation-individuation from the family group is *not* greeted by a ritualized welcoming into the greater community (except, perhaps, in gang initiations). More often, the adolescent is absorbed into the mass psyche of the collective peer group. The narrow confines of the peer-group imagination, external factors in our social environment, new standardization policies in education, and peer-group bullying in schools repress the tendency toward individuation. These forces drive young people toward alienation and destructive behaviors, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, toward a mass psyche dominated by a superego of ideologies and 'isms'.

Erich Neumann argues that "The super-ego is not, like the Self, an individual authority of the personality, it is a later introjected collective authority which endeavors to impose the demands of ... the collectivity, on the individual by violence" (Neumann, *Child* 204). The violence is evident in the ways young people repress, or are forced by group pressure to repress, their own true nature — their soul identity — in order to conform to the collective ideal of ego development. Such behaviors can begin, at the ages of nine or ten, as bullying of anyone who acts differently from the peer group, and can become endemic by the time the student reaches junior high and high school. Gebser further illuminates this dichotomy within the personality:

The current situation manifests on the one hand an egocentric individualism exaggerated to extremes and desirous of possessing everything, while on the other it manifests an equally extreme collectivism that promises the total fulfillment of man's being.... [As a result] the individual is being driven into isolation while the collective degenerates into a mere aggregation. (Gebser 3)

Since the spiritual foundations of both the culture and the self are expressed symbolically in the archetypes of the collective unconscious, our greatest challenge in raising and educating children is to nurture archetypal influences on the developing personality so that they can temper the introjected influences of the superego.

In many young adolescents there is a real conflict between individuation and satisfactory social adaptation — between development of the personality from within and adaptation to a place in the social economy that is defined from without. Young people are instinctively aware of this conflict, and there is a real struggle in many young people over the question of which authority is going to dominate the psyche. A cultural educational curriculum that gives young people the a-perceptive tools they need to interpret the archetypal symbols gives them a better foundation for answering that question for themselves. Thus to promote the goals of individuation-integrality requires a new cultural education curriculum that incorporates the history of the evolution of consciousness structures (Mitchell).

5. Conclusion

The objective of a re-visualized cultural curriculum is to take the young adolescent through these various emergent structures in the evolution of consciousness as they lead toward integrality — that is, toward “the unfolding and intensification of consciousness, [that] manifests itself as an increasingly intense luminescence of the spiritual in man” (Gebser 542). The objective of this curriculum is not to arrive at integrality any more than it is to arrive at individuation, but only to set the individual on a pathway that allows the process of individuation-integrality to unfold naturally and progress, undeterred by the demands of the collectivity. Thus, the educational objective is to transform the deficient modes of the archaic, magical, mythological, and mental structures of consciousness into efficient modes that work together. As Gebser puts it,

By returning to the very sources of human development as we observe the structures of consciousness ... [unfold] ... we can not only discover the past ... but also gain a view into the future which reveals the traits of a new reality amidst the decline of our age. (Gebser 2)

Should this not be the primary goal of education?

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